

Quest for Identity in Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns*

Bhawani Shankar Adhikari, Ph.D

Associate professor, Department of English, Balmiki Campus, Exhibition Road,
Kathmandu, Nepal Sanskrit University, Dang, Nepal

Article History:

Received: 06.03.2025 Revised: 26.03.2025 Accepted: 31.03.2025 Published: 05.04.2025

Abstract

Quest for identity aims to examine gender inequality as reflected in the novel *A Thousand Splendid Suns* through the character analysis of Rasheed, the dominant male character, and the female characters Mariam and Laila, two wives of Rasheed, who marries Laila as his second wife for the sake of producing the son, but he physically abuses both his wives. Then both of them get together and fight against Rasheed and Mariam kills him and she goes to jail and Laila starts her new life with her own identity. Mariam has created her own identity by fighting against the injustice of the patriarchy of the existing system and so has Laila. The primary data have been taken from the novel *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and the secondary data have been used as the articles published in various journals related to the novel and the theory of patriarchy has become analogous in it.

Keywords: *Burqa, gender, harami, identity, patriarchal.*

Suggested citation: Adhikari, B.S. (2025). Quest for Identity in Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns*. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), 395-408. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(2\).34](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(2).34)

Introduction

The process of establishing one's identity is often a struggle to secure a rightful place in society. It involves a challenging effort to claim an individual's legitimate position in the ongoing competition for social status. For those without a clear identity, it is only natural to strive for both recognition and lawful standing. In this context, contesting identity is as vital to human existence as the very essence of life itself within a societal framework. In Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, Mariam and Laila, the novel's central female characters, engage in a relentless battle throughout the story to assert their dignified and respected identities in their social lives. Their identities evolve from daughters to wives to mothers, reflecting their changing roles in society. Laila, for example, finds herself imprisoned after killing her husband, Rasheed, in

a confrontation, while Mariam becomes a teacher, establishing a school in her own right.

Hosseini's novel explores the identity crisis experienced by the female characters and their shared struggle to carve out their own identities in Afghanistan. The protagonists strive to maintain a dignified and respected sense of self in a society that is heavily patriarchal. The quest for identity in the male-dominated culture of Afghanistan is a significant challenge for the women, symbolizing the hardships they face. The novel illustrates how Mariam and Laila, the two central female figures, suffer from a crisis of both social and cultural identity. They are both married to Rasheed, a controlling man who also grapples with his own quest for identity. His desire to have a son, which he eventually achieves through Laila, is an expression of his patriarchal beliefs rather than a genuine pursuit

of identity. Even after fathering a son, Rasheed continues to mistreat both women, highlighting that his longing for a son is not about personal fulfillment but about reinforcing societal gender norms.

The identity crisis begins with Mariam's birth, as she is labeled a "harami," meaning an illegitimate child. Mariam learns from her mother, Nana, that she has no rightful claim to things others have, such as love, family, home, and acceptance, because she is the bastard daughter of Jalil, a wealthy and high-status man who refuses to acknowledge Mariam and Nana publicly as his daughter and wife.

Mariam's journey involves efforts to visit her father's home, only to lose her mother in the process. At the age of fifteen, she is forced to marry Rasheed, who is twenty years older than her, and endures the tragedy of giving birth to seven daughters who die prematurely. She also accepts Laila as Rasheed's second wife, assists her in delivering a son, and fights alongside her for their identities and happiness, as well as the well-being of Laila's son, Aziza. In the end, Mariam sacrifices herself, going to prison as a criminal, marking her ongoing struggle and quest for self-identity.

To address the issue of the search for identity, the theoretical framework draws on the works of authors like Judith Butler, Simone de Beauvoir, Amílcar Cabral, Linda Martin Alcoff, and other relevant identity crisis theories.

In many societies, women are viewed as the weaker gender, often lacking independent identities of their own. They are perceived as needing male relationships to establish their social and cultural identities. This gender divide is a key part of the sociocultural structure. Simone de Beauvoir, in her essay *Introduction from The Second Sex*, discusses this notion, quoting Aristotle who stated, "The female is a female by virtue of a certain lack of qualities." He further asserts that women are "afflicted with a natural defectiveness." St. Thomas also regarded women as "imperfect men" and "incidental beings." This idea is reflected in Genesis, where Eve is described as having been made from what Bossuet called "a supernumerary bone" of Adam (p. 150).

It is often said that women are not recognized as autonomous individuals. Instead, their identity is defined by men, in relation to their roles as wives or daughters. Beauvoir points out that women are lost without men, stating, "Man can think of himself without the woman. She can't think of herself without man" (p. 150). This highlights that a woman's identity cannot be conceived independently; she must be connected to a male figure to have a defined place in society.

In patriarchal societies, women lack independent existence. Judith Butler, in her essay *Gender Trouble, Feminist Theory, and Psychoanalytic Discourse*, argues that "Strictly speaking, women cannot be said to exist" (p. 202). This suggests that women's identities are dependent on their relationships with men. Without these connections, their sense of self is diminished. Similarly, Amílcar Cabral addresses the issue of identity, emphasizing the marginalization of women. He writes in *Identity and Dignity in the Concept of National Liberation Struggle* that women are trapped by the cultural and social contradictions of their lives and cannot break free from their marginalized position. He states, "They cannot escape from their role as a marginal class, or a 'marginalized' class" (p. 57).

This demonstrates that the marginalized position of women is a key factor in their struggle to find a stable identity. However, identity is also fluid and can change over time. As Beauvoir states, "identity is not a constant, precisely because the biological and sociological factors which define it are in constant change...The sociological factors are more determining than the biological...The social condition is an objective agent arising from economic, political, social and cultural aspects which are characteristic of the growth and history of the society in question" (p. 58-59).

This suggests that identity is not solely a matter of gender but also reflects broader social, political, and economic conditions. The marginalization faced by women is linked to the larger issues of class inequality, as those in the lower classes—women included—share similar struggles. In society, everyone must fight for individuality and a personal sense of identity. Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns* has

garnered significant attention from both scholars and readers since its release in 2007. The novel has been interpreted through various theoretical lenses, leading to differing critiques depending on the perspective of the critic. Rebecca Stuhr asserts that the novel represents both the history of Afghanistan and the struggles faced by women in the country. She suggests that the central theme revolves around the changing political landscape of Afghanistan and the tragic situation of its women. Stuhr writes, "The plight of women and the history of Afghanistan: Themes in *A Thousand Splendid Suns*... a country of social, cultural and economic diversity, a country that has undergone destructive political upheaval, a country of beauty and history, and a country of desolation and deprivation" (p. 60). Additionally, some critics highlight that the novel addresses the issue of domestic abuse.

Hosseini delves into themes of gender equality, gender stereotypes, and domestic abuse in *A Thousand Splendid Suns* (p. 65). Rebecca Stuhr notes that Laila and Tariq return to Afghanistan with renewed hope for the country's future, yet the novel's conclusion suggests the country's instability. While Laila witnesses the transformation of Kabul as its residents begin to repair and rebuild, she is also aware that all is not well, as the effects of bombing and destruction persist (p. 66). This illustrates that despite their hope for a new era, Laila realizes that Afghanistan remains in a fragile state.

The ongoing conflict in Afghanistan has also deeply impacted the nation's healthcare system. In her 2000 book *Women of the Afghan War*, Deborah Ellis writes, "The war and the chaos that comes with it have crippled the healthcare delivery system... women who are trained and could be of use are largely forced to remain at home. Although some women are permitted to provide health care for other women, the hospitals and clinics set aside for female patients are few and ill-equipped" (p. 97).

Similarly, Hafizullah Emadi discusses the effect of gender ideology on women's health in his book *Repression, Resistance, and Women in Afghanistan*. He points out that there are very few health centers in Afghanistan, especially in the capital of each province. Women are often

neglected by their husbands and excluded from healthcare. In emergency situations, medical treatment is sometimes provided without the woman being seen directly by a male doctor, further exacerbating the lack of proper care (Emadi, 47). These issues of gender and ethnic discrimination are key themes in *A Thousand Splendid Suns*.

Nelofer Pazira, a filmmaker and journalist who lived in Kabul until 1989, writes about her personal experiences in her memoir *A Bed of Red Flowers: In Search of My Afghanistan* (2005). The memoir chronicles her childhood in Afghanistan, her family's escape to Pakistan and Canada, and her return to Afghanistan. She also recounts her experience filming *Kandahar*, an Iranian-made film based on her journey back to Afghanistan to search for a childhood friend. The film uses the visual symbolism of the burqa, worn by Pazira and other local women as they navigate their environment, highlighting the struggles women face in the context of their society (p. 83). The Free Library of Philadelphia "offers podcasts of their author events. On May 24, 2007, Khaled Hosseini was the guest author at the Free Library" (p. 98).

Ian McGillis writes, "Melodramatic? In any other context, yes, but here such charges are easily countered by the nonfiction accounts of Afghan women themselves, whose world really was one where the line between right and wrong was clearly drawn. Similarly, complaints that the narrative is ploddingly linear simply get trampled in the momentum of the story and the need for its being told. This, one comes to see, is the key to Hosseini's commercial appeal: he has the common touch. Armed with that gift, he is able, without downplaying or cheapening the horror his characters suffer, to infuse their lives with the possibility of redemption" (p. 104). This suggests that Hosseini's commercial success lies in his ability to connect with readers on a human level, presenting the suffering of his characters without diminishing the gravity of their experiences. The nonfiction accounts of Afghan women, who truly live in such a world of hardship, further underscore the reality of their struggles.

Sunita Mehta compiles essays from a 2001 conference held at the Graduate Centre for the City University of New York, where Afghan women scholars and activists discussed the history of Afghan women's rights, the rights granted to women under Islam, the abuses inflicted by the Taliban, and women's priorities in post-Taliban Afghanistan (x). The contributors, feminists from various countries, include women who have worked in Afghanistan as teachers, aid workers, and organizers.

Despite the substantial body of criticism from scholars, it appears that the issue addressed by the current researcher has not yet been fully explored. Therefore, this study offers a new perspective on *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, aiming to deepen the understanding of Afghan women's struggles in their quest for identity.

Statement of Problems

Khaled Hosseini's novel *A Thousand Splendid Suns* depicts how the main female characters struggle in society to get an identity. Mariam and Laila are in the process of reaching their identity from daughter to wife and individual identity or social strata by fighting against their husband, Rasheed in Afghanistan. Identity is not fixed: it is slippery. In the quest for identity, females are hindered by the patriarchy. In this sense:

- A) How do Mariam and Laila attempt to establish their identity?
- B) What are the various obstacles for Mariam and Laila to establish their identity?

Objectives of the Research

The general objectives of the research are to explore the women's identity in the Muslim society but the specific objectives are:

- A) To investigate how Mariam and Laila attempt to establish their identity.
- B) To explore what the various obstacles are for Mariam and Laila to establish their identity.

Research Methodology

To achieve the research objectives, this research has gathered historical data through content analysis, utilizing primary data from *the novel A*

Thousand Splendid Suns and secondary data from relevant academic journal articles. The research employs a library-based method for collecting historical data, a technique identified by Hamzah (2019) as particularly effective for qualitative research and examining theoretical foundations. Similarly, Kurniawan et al. (2023) applied this method for historical data collection. This research adopts a similar approach to explore the historical perspectives on social structures and gender inequality as presented in *the novel A Thousand Splendid Suns*.

To further support the research goals, thematic excerpts from *the novel A Thousand Splendid Suns* were collected, treating literary sources as valuable qualitative data. In line with the perspective of Abidin and Laskar (2020), this research emphasizes that analyzing historical texts goes beyond just examining their content; it also requires interpreting the deeper meanings embedded within the text. Additionally, confirming the alignment between textual and contextual analysis is crucial for fully understanding the significance of the text. In this regard, *A Thousand Splendid Suns* serves as a valuable source for investigating various aspects of social structures that reinforced the prominence of the male in ancient society. The research employs content analysis, utilizing both primary and secondary sources, to conduct a thorough examination.

Moreover, the secondary data sources include library resources, gender studies, research papers, and relevant texts. The study predominantly relies on library-based research. Since direct observation of this ancient societal structure is not feasible, the research is grounded in the assumption that every social system has historical roots. Historical data are gathered through content analysis of *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and secondary sources from research journals. As noted by Hamzah (2019) and Kurniawan et al. (2023), this approach is particularly effective in qualitative research for exploring theoretical foundations. This study applies this method to analyze gender roles within *A Thousand Splendid Suns*.

Additionally, the methodology is based on analyzing both primary and secondary data from

various journals and sources concerning the condition of women as depicted in the primary text. This approach follows a similar methodology used by Adhikari (2020, 2024), Adhikari et al. (2020, 2022), and other researchers such as Adhikari who employed qualitative research methods. Likewise, Adhikari et al. (2024), and Guragain et al. (2024) and Adhikari (2024) have utilized similar research methodologies in their qualitative studies, which align with the approach used in this paper for a detailed analysis of the primary text data.

Theory of Patriarchy

Gender role inequalities are deeply connected to the concept of patriarchy, a system marked by hierarchical power structures and unequal relationships. This system reinforces societal norms related to masculinity and femininity, perpetuating the persistent power disparity between men and women. Walby (1990) characterizes patriarchy as a male-dominated family structure and a broader social and ideological framework that places men above women. In patriarchal societies, the role of motherhood is highlighted, focusing on the responsibilities of nurturing, educating, and raising children within the family. Within this structure, women's roles, identities, and inherent worth are often neglected and devalued. The concept of patriarchy serves as the analytical framework for exploring the representation of establishing the women's identity in *A Thousand Splendid Suns*.

Women's Struggle

The principal women characters in the novel struggle for their best for their personal identity and their struggle has become the model for all other Afghani women and for the entire women of the world in a sense.

Mariam's Struggle

Mariam is the main female character, a harami, or illegitimate daughter, of Jalil. He urged his slave, Nana—Mariam's mother—to keep her distance as soon as she became pregnant, fearing the loss of his social standing. As a result, Mariam lost her sense of social identity, only seeing her beloved father once a week during

their fishing trips. He read to her and gave her lovely gifts, but she could never truly live with him. After deciding to visit his home, which he did not acknowledge, she returned to find that her mother had taken her own life.

When Jalil came to see Mariam, he comforted her and spoke about his home. Nana warned Mariam that Jalil was not as kind as he appeared, but Mariam dismissed her mother's concerns. She believed that Nana was obstructing her happiness and that she twisted the truth of their lives, making Mariam yet another victim of her grievances against the world. Mariam might have said *"You're afraid, Nana, they might have said. You're afraid that I might find the happiness you ever had. And you don't want me to be happy. You don't want a good life for me you're the one with the wretched heart"* (p. 28)

This shows that Mariam placed her trust in her father's words and questioned her mother's warnings about Jalil's dishonesty. She chose to believe her father without reservation and longed to visit his home. After Jalil comforted her during his visit to Nana's house and then left, Mariam felt uneasy and began to dream about his home, wishing to share that identity with him. At night, Mariam lay in her cot, imagining what Jalil's house in Herat was like. She envisioned living with him and seeing him every day. She pictured herself handing him a towel after he shaved and telling him when he cut himself. She imagined brewing tea for him and sewing on his missing buttons. They would stroll through the vaulted bazaar in Herat, where Jalil claimed you could find anything. They would ride in his car, and people would point and say, "There goes Jalil Khan with his daughter." He would show her the famous tree where a poet was buried (p. 24).

Mariam longs to establish her identity as Jalil's daughter. She dreams of living in his house and walking together in Herat, especially in the bazaar where Jalil had told her she could find anything she desired. Her wish is to ride in his car, recognized by others as his daughter, with people pointing and saying, "There goes Jalil Khan with his daughter." She also hopes to learn more about the famous tree where a well-known poet is buried. However, her desire for social identity as Jalil Khan's daughter remains

unfulfilled. Mariam doesn't want to lose her mother; she seeks recognition as Jalil's daughter, which would also grant her mother, Nana, the identity of being Jalil Khan's wife.

Mariam disregarded her mother's warning that she would die if she left and went to Jalil Khan's house. When she arrived, none of the household members recognized her, and she was not allowed entry. She introduced herself, saying, "I'm here to see Jalil Khan. I'm Mariam. His daughter" (p. 32). A girl, confused, told her to "Wait here" (p. 32) before going to check. However, Jalil Khan's driver informed Mariam, "Jalil Khan is not here... he's away on urgent business" (p. 32). Despite this, Mariam refused to leave, insisting she would wait for him to return, no matter how long it took. Although the driver closed the gates, she continued to wait. "Mariam sat, drawing her knees to her chest. It was already early evening, and she was beginning to feel hungry. She ate the driver's toffee. A while later, the driver came out again and said, 'You need to go home now. It'll be dark in less than an hour'" (p. 32-33).

Mariam ignored the darkness and her hunger, stubbornly deciding to wait outside for her father in hopes of establishing her social identity. In reality, Jalil Khan was not away on business; he was at home, unwilling to acknowledge her as his daughter. The driver had been instructed to take her to a hotel and to prevent her from entering the house, knowing it might be days before Jalil returned. However, Mariam refused to leave and spent the night outside Jalil's home.

She watched as the sky darkened and shadows enveloped the nearby houses. The tattooed girl brought her some bread and a plate of rice, which Mariam declined, but the girl left it beside her. Occasionally, Mariam heard footsteps in the street, doors opening, and muffled greetings. Electric lights flickered on, illuminating the dimly lit windows, and dogs barked. When hunger became too much to bear, she finally ate the rice and bread. As she listened to the crickets chirping and watched clouds drift past the pale moon, she eventually fell asleep. In the morning, she was gently shaken awake to find that someone had covered her with a blanket during the night (p. 33).

This passage illustrates Mariam's determination to spend the night outside Jalil's house in pursuit of her social identity. She was so focused that she didn't even want to eat the food offered by the tattooed girl, remaining aware of the night's happenings, including the barking dogs. Although she initially refused the bread and rice left for her, she eventually succumbed to her hunger and ate. As she noticed someone had covered her with a blanket during the night, it highlighted her struggle. Rubbing her eyes, she resolutely stated, "I'm going to wait for him" (p. 33).

Mariam did everything she could to reach Jalil, but his driver insisted, "Jalil Khan says that I need to take you back now. Right now. Do you understand? Jalil Khan says so" (p. 34). The driver forced her into the car, yet Mariam was desperate to see her father before returning to Nana's house. "I want to see him," she pleaded, tears welling in her eyes (p. 34). Unfortunately, Mariam didn't get the chance to meet him; she was forcibly placed in the car and taken away by the driver.

Then a pair of hands buried into her armpits and she was lifted off the ground. Mariam kicked. The pebbles spilled from her pocket. Mariam kept kicking and crying as she was carried to the car and lowered onto the cold leather of the backseat (p. 34). Mariam was unable to get her father Jalil. She was driven back to Nana in Herat. She kicked and cried but it was in vain. "All during the ride, as she bounced in the backseat, she cried. They were tears of grief, of anger, of disillusionment. But mainly tears of a deep, deep shame at how foolishly she had given herself over to the Jalil" (p. 34-35). It indicates that Mariam's struggle for her social identity was nothing more than struggle. It was beyond her power. She had to realize her mother's warning of distrusting her father. What she got by ignoring her mother's warning and visiting her father's house to be identified as the daughter of Jalil was only to lose her mother Nana whom she found being hanged by herself. When they buried Nana in a corner of the cemetery in Gul Daman, then Mariam was taken in the house of Jalil. Mariam couldn't get any comfort in Jalil's house because two days before she wasn't allowed to go in and now, she felt like another

life time that there was upside down of her life within two days. She couldn't forget her mother. "All she could hear was Nana saying, *I'll die if you go. I'll just die.*" (p. 38).

Jalil Khan's family members were bewildered and did not recognize Mariam as one of their own. His wives and daughters did not welcome her warmly, leading Mariam to understand that Nana had been right. She realized she did not belong in Jalil Khan's house and began to question her place there. *But where do I belong? What am I going to do now? I'm all you have in this world, Mariam, and when I'm gone, you'll have nothing. You'll have nothing. You are nothing!* (p. 40).

Mariam was not welcomed by Jalil Khan's family, and Jalil himself showed no responsibility for her happiness or well-being. None of the family members were friendly or kind to her. In fact, Jalil and his wives had found a suitor for Mariam named Rasheed, a merchant originally from Kandahar who lived in a two-story house in Kabul's Deh-Mazing district. Although Mariam was only fifteen, Rasheed was significantly older, around forty or forty-five. Despite her reluctance to marry, Mariam felt she had no place to go and hoped Jalil would protect her from this fate. However, she soon realized that Jalil wanted her to marry Rasheed as well. Ultimately, Mariam accepted the marriage for the sake of establishing her social identity as Rasheed's wife, remaining silent about her feelings. "Mariam stayed quiet. Throats were cleared" (p. 52).

In the mirror, Mariam had her first glimpse of Rasheed: the big, square, ruddy face; the hooked nose; the flushed cheeks that gave the impression of sly cheerfulness; the watery, bloodshot eyes; the crowded teeth, the front two pushed together like a gabled roof; the impossibly low hair line, barely two finger widths above the busy eye brows; the wall of thick, coarse, salt- and-pepper hair. Their gazes met briefly in the glass and slid away. *This is the face of my husband, Mariam thought*" (p. 53)

The description of Rasheed indicates he is not a suitable match for Mariam. She certainly would not have married him if Jalil Khan had acknowledged her as his daughter and provided her with a social identity. However, neither Jalil

nor his wives and children accepted Mariam as a legitimate member of the family. In this circumstance, Mariam had no choice but to marry the physically and mentally unsuitable Rasheed, as doing so would grant her the social identity she sought in society. This reflects the idea that women are often seen as incomplete and unable to establish their identity without men. Mariam's struggle is about seeking identity through her relationships with men—from her father to her husband, as illustrated in the text. When it came time to put the ring on Rasheed's finger, Mariam's hands trembled, and she needed his assistance to do so: "Mariam's hands shook when she tried to slip the band onto his finger, and Rasheed had to help her" (p. 53). In this context, Mariam's quest for identity through her connection to a man appears both meaningful and acceptable as:

When the wedding ring was handed to Rasheed, then they had to sign the contract. Mariam signed her name to a document and the priest declared that they were husband and wife and they got congratulations. "You are now husband and wife" the mullah said. Tabreek. Congratulations" (p. 54).

Mariam gained her social identity only when the priest declared her and Rasheed husband and wife, congratulating them. This marked her achievement of both social and legal status as a married woman. Despite the unhappiness and unsuitability of the match, she attained her position and dignity in society.

Once married to Rasheed, Mariam felt she had to be the ideal wife. She needed to cook delicious meals to win his approval and was constantly anxious about whether she was meeting his expectations in both her work and her cooking. Her concerns reflect her struggle to obtain a respectable identity as:

This was the first meal she had cooked for him and Mariam wished she had been in a better state when she made it, she had still been shaken from the incident at the tan door as she had cooked and all day she had fretted about the deal's consistency, its colour, worried that he would think she had stirred in too much ginger or not enough turmeric" (p. 68).

Mariam's struggle does not end with her marriage to Rasheed; it continues as she tries to make him happy and satisfy him with her service. She fears that her husband's displeasure could lead to losing not only him but also the social identity she gained through marriage.

After marrying Rasheed, various women visit her home, introducing themselves as wives, including one named Fariba, who identifies herself as the wife of Hakim. They discuss the importance of having children, suggesting that it is better to have a boy since sons carry on the family name and identity. They advise her, "A boy is better, Mariam Jan; they carry the family name" (p. 66). Mariam attempts to fulfill this expectation by trying to give birth to a son, but her efforts prove futile. She is unable to bear a single living child out of seven attempts.

Mariam was not accustomed to wearing a burqa before her marriage. It was a social and traditional requirement, and she felt confined by it. Rasheed had to assist her in putting it on. The padded headpiece felt tight and heavy on her head, and viewing the world through a mesh screen was unfamiliar. She practiced walking around her room while wearing it but kept tripping over the hem. The loss of her peripheral vision was unsettling, and she disliked how the pleated fabric pressed against her mouth, making her feel suffocated (p. 71).

This passage illustrates how women must adapt to new customs and systems to establish their identities in a patriarchal society, as seen with Mariam's uncomfortable experience of wearing a burqa in Rasheed's household. Her efforts reflect her struggle for social identity as his wife.

Women are often viewed as innocent and ignorant, lacking knowledge. When Mariam asked Rasheed about communists and their beliefs, he did not respond kindly. His dismissive reply was, "You know nothing, do you? You are like a child. Your brain is empty. There is no information in it" (p. 97). Despite Mariam's attempts to understand the beliefs and struggles of communists, Rasheed silenced her. She was fearful of losing the identity tied to her role as Rasheed's wife and felt compelled to endure her difficulties and challenges.

Mariam found it challenging to endure Rasheed's demeaning treatment—his scorn, ridiculous insults, and the way he dismissed her as if she were just a house cat. However, after four years of marriage, she realized how much a woman can tolerate out of fear (p. 97).

This clearly shows that women often endure various insults and mistreatment from their husbands even after marriage, all in the name of maintaining their social identity. Mariam felt she had no choice but to accept Rasheed's abuse, essentially becoming his house cat. Her experience reflects the struggles of many women like her in Afghanistan. Although marriage granted her a social identity, the fight to uphold that dignity was ongoing for women.

When women marry, they are often expected to bear children, particularly sons, to ensure the longevity of their marriages. Failing to do so can make them feel like burdens to their husbands and sources of unhappiness, which may lead to the threat of being replaced by a second wife. Mariam tried to give birth to a son but suffered seven failures, causing her to be seen as a burden by her husband, Rasheed, who was frustrated and distressed by her inability to provide a male heir. Mariam's struggles are portrayed in a way that resonates deeply with many women readers, evoking tears.

In the four years since that day at the bathhouse, Mariam had experienced six more cycles of hope followed by disappointment. Each loss, each visit to the doctor, felt more devastating than the last. With every setback, Rasheed had become increasingly distant and resentful. No matter what Mariam did, it failed to please him. She kept the house clean, ensured he had a steady supply of fresh shirts, and prepared his favorite meals. In a misguided attempt to impress him, she even tried wearing makeup once, but when he saw her, he recoiled in disgust. Mortified, she hurried to the bathroom to wash it off, tears of shame mixing with the soap. She felt the weight of her failures—she could not give him the son he desired. Seven times she had let him down, and now she felt like nothing more than a burden to him (p. 98).

Mariam desired to be a beautiful and loving wife to Rasheed, hoping to fulfill his dream by giving

him a son. After seven unsuccessful attempts, she felt like nothing more than a burden to him. He didn't appreciate her efforts to look attractive or wear makeup, leading her to wash it off in shame. This highlighted the double standard she faced—marriage and motherhood were essential for her to maintain her identity.

As Mariam continued to fail in bearing a son, Rasheed's dissatisfaction grew. He began to criticize her cooking, even angrily pushing a plate of rice away and storming out of the house. When he returned, he brought pebbles for her to chew, causing her to break two molars and bleed—a depiction of the inhumane treatment she endured.

He snatched her hand, opened it, and dropped a handful of pebbles into it. "Put these in your mouth" ... his powerful hands clasped her jaw. He shoved two fingers into her mouth and pried it open, then forced the cold hard pebbles into it. Mariam struggle against him, mumbling, but he kept pushing the pebbles in... "Now Chew" he said. Through the mouthful of grit and pebbles, Mariam mumbled a plea. Tears were leaking out of the corners of her eyes. "CHEW!" he bellowed.... Mariam chewed. Something in the back of her mouth cracked. "Good" Rasheed said... "Now you know what your rice tastes like. Now you know what you have given me in the marriage. Bad food and nothing else". Then he was gone, leaving Mariam to spit out pebbles, blood, and the fragments of two broken molars (p. 102-103).

Rasheed's mistreatment of Mariam is not only inhumane but also unimaginable. Mariam endured this cruelty from her husband under the guise of her social identity as his wife. In addition, Rasheed took another woman, Laila, as his second wife in hopes of having a son with her.

Laila's Entry in the Family

There is a contrast between these two women. The difference is that Laila did not have the identity crisis of heaving her father, Babi as Mariam faced being born, a harami. Babi wanted his daughter Laila to give high dignity and social respect by educating her properly. Babi was taking Laila in a safe place for her education but

he had not disclosed her where they were going. It is narrated "He would not disclose anything to Laila about their destination except to say that with it he was contributing to her education" (p. 143-144). Laila's father was dedicated and responsible, striving for his daughter's bright future. Unfortunately, Laila lost her parents in the war, leaving her in need of support and social identity. As a result, she became Rasheed's second wife, whether by choice or circumstance. This was a turn of events, as Laila was initially seeking identity through marriage to Tariq, the man she loved deeply. Her efforts in this regard are expressed in the following way.

A groan came out of Laila. Then a wail, and then she was eying and when he went to wipe her cheek with the pad of his thumb, she swiped his hand away. It was selfish and irrational, but she was furious with him for a banding her Tariq who was like an extension of her, whose shadow sprung beside hers in every memory. How could he leave her? (p.178).

Laila's longing represents her desire to have Tariq as her husband, which would give her a sense of identity in society. Although Tariq planned to go to Pakistan, he was in love with her, and Laila couldn't fathom being left behind. She feared that without Tariq, she would be lost and without identity. Rasheed discovered Laila amidst the rubble of war, having lost her parents and being the sole survivor. Mariam was opposed to Rasheed bringing Laila into their home. For eighteen years, she had never questioned him, but now she felt compelled to speak up against his decision to marry Laila. Mariam's request is produced like this:

People will talk. It looks dishonourable, an unmarried you woman living here. It is bad for my reputation. And hers. And yours. I might add "eighteen years" Mariam said. "And I have never asked you for a thing. Not one thing. I am asking how" ... "she can't just here, if that's what you are suggesting. I can't go on feeding her and clothing her and giving her a place to sleep. I'm not the Red Cross, Mariam" (p. 208).

Mariam was unwilling to accept Laila as Rasheed's second wife, fearing it would undermine her own identity. She was acutely aware of the implications of having a young girl

in their home and asked Rasheed to remove Laila, marking the first request she had made in eighteen years of marriage. Mariam was not prepared to serve Laila and warned Rasheed that she wasn't a caretaker. However, Rasheed dismissed her concerns, asserting that the decision was ultimately between him and Laila. He stated, "It's not your decision; it is hers and mine" (p. 208). He also reminded Mariam that polygamy was common in their society, noting that not only did his friends have multiple wives, but her own father had three as well. Despite this, Mariam firmly opposed the idea of Laila becoming Rasheed's second wife, insisting, "I won't allow it" (p. 209). Her refusal reflected her struggle to maintain her social identity, yet despite her efforts, Rasheed proceeded to take Laila as his wife, arranging everything for the wedding and declaring himself her husband. It is expressed:

I am your husband now, and it falls on me to guard not only your honour but ours ... that is the husband's burden.... I also ask that when we are out together, that you wear a burqa. For your own protection, naturally. It is best. So many lewd men in this town now. Such vile intentions, so eager to dishonour even a married woman. So That's all" (p. 217).

Rasheed grants Laila the identity of his wife, positioning himself as her protector in society. He insists that she wear a burqa for her safety and honor. However, when Rasheed takes Laila as his second wife, Mariam's dream of being his only spouse is shattered, and her sense of identity is diminished. She expresses her regret for caring for Laila, saying, "I would not have fed you and washed you and nursed you if I'd known you were going to turn around and steal my husband" (p. 219). Mariam was unaware that such a situation could arise and would have acted differently had she known Laila would become Rasheed's second wife.

At this time, Laila is already pregnant with Tariq's child, although Rasheed is unaware of this. He is excited about having a son and takes pride in it, exclaiming, "swelling so quality," and declaring, "It is going to be a big boy. My son will be a Palawan! Like his father" (p. 226). This highlights Rasheed's desire to be a father to a

son, but his hopes are dashed when Laila gives birth to a daughter, Aziza. Following her birth, Rasheed shows little care for the baby girl and begins to resent Laila.

In this challenging environment, Mariam and Laila develop a supportive and cooperative relationship, working together to assert their identities. Mariam empathizes with Laila, warning her, "He'll turn on you too, you know. Soon enough. And you gave him a daughter. So, you see, your sin is even less forgivable than mine" (p. 243-244). Mariam and Laila came to understand Rasheed's true nature and shifted their relationship from being his wives to being close friends. Mariam expressed to Laila that having a daughter with Rasheed was seen as misfortune in their lives. They recognized that they were allies rather than adversaries in their pursuit of happiness and identity within society.

Mariam and Laila's Attempt to Escape

Mariam and Laila attempted to escape Rasheed's house in search of their own identities, but they were intercepted and taken to the police station for questioning. Rasheed brought them back home and brutally beat both of them. He locked them inside, securing the doors and windows, yet they continued to seek a way to escape. The scene is described.

Laila did not see the punch coming one moment she was talking and the next she was on all fours, wide eyed and red-faced, trying to draw a breath. It was as if a car had hit at full speed, in the tender place between the lower tip of the breastbone and the belly button. She realized that she had dropped Aziza, the Aziza was screaming.... She was being dragged by the hair.... she saw his foot kick open the door to Mariam's room, saw Aziza flung on to the bed.... Downstairs, the beating began. There was blood on his hands, blood on Mariam's face, her hair, down her neck and back. Her shirt had been ripped down the front.... He shut the double doors to the shed, took a key from his pocket, worked the padlock.... Rasheed had filled the cracks between the boards with something put a range and immovable objects at the foot of the

door so no light came from under it. Something had been stuffed in the key hole (p. 261-263).

Mariam and Laila's attempts to escape the locked doors and windows symbolize their struggle for independence and identity, which is thwarted by the oppressive force of patriarchy. Rasheed embodies this patriarchal dominance, reflecting the dire situation faced by women in Afghanistan. Their experiences represent the harsh reality for all Afghan women.

When Laila gave birth to a son, Zalmai, Rasheed fulfilled his dream of having a son to carry on his name, moving the baby into the bed he shared with Laila (p. 258). Despite this, both Mariam and Laila continued to endure immense suffering at the hands of Rasheed, who treated them as objects devoid of identity, subjecting them to regular beatings. Their struggle for autonomy persisted amid this ongoing abuse. His misbehaviour is narrated:

He was on Laila, pummelling her chest, her head, her belly with fists, tearing her hair, throwing her to the wall. Rasheed... pushed Laila to the ground and began kicking her. Mariam threw herself on Laila. He went on kicking Mariam now ... kicking until he could not anymore (p. 298).

The way Laila and Mariam are treated as identity-less objects highlights the broader system in Afghanistan that undermines women's identities. This serves as evidence of the unimaginable plight faced by Afghan women, emphasizing the urgent need for improvement in their circumstances.

Laila and Mariam ultimately struggled to free themselves from Rasheed's physical and mental torment. In their fight against him, Mariam realized that Rasheed was about to take Laila's life. The author captures the intensity of this struggle.

He was still on the top of Laila, his eyes wild and crazy, his hands wrapped around her neck. Laila's face was turning blue now and her eyes had rolled back. Mariam saw that she was no longer struggling. He's going to kill her she thought.... in Rasheed's eyes she was murder for them both.... Mariam brought down the shovel.

This time she gave it everything she had (p. 339-341).

Mariam knew Rasheed was going to kill both Laila and herself. So, she brought down the shovel and gave it everything she had. Rasheed was dead. They thought they had to move the dead body away so that the child, Zalmai, could not see this" (p. 344). Then they took Rasheed into the tool shed and left him behind the workbench. Mariam confessed her deed. "It is fair" Mariam said. "I killed our husband" (p. 349). There was no personal freedom and identity of women, Mariam remembered that her mother, Nana's said to her. "*Like a compass needle that points north, a man's accusing finger always finds a woman*" (p. 354, italic sized in the original text). Mariam confessed her murdering Rasheed in the court but even there she found the Judge treated female as identity less object.

"I wonder" the young Talib said, "God has made us differently, you women and us men. Our brains are different. You are not able to think like we can. Western doctors and their science have proven this. This is why we require only one male witness but two females' ones" (p. 355). This reflects an effort to obscure female identity, even within government institutions like the court. While there may be biological differences between men and women, it is fundamentally unjust to dismiss female witnesses and insist on male testimony. Mariam stated, "I admit to what I did, brother... But if I had not, he would have killed her. He was strangely her" (p. 356). Despite Mariam's willingness to accept her sentence, the judge still demanded a male witness. This raises the question: where is the identity of women in society?

Laila's New Life

Laila started living with Tariq and her children in Murree. Now she got her own identity with her choice but Mariam went in the prison. Laila request Tariq to be back in Afghanistan from Pakistan. Tariq wants to know if she is unhappy there. "Are you unhappy here! You seem happy. The children are too" (p. 379). Then they decided to return Kabul but Laila likes to go her village Herat first, "But first, I want to go to Herat" she says" (p. 379). In fact, the idea of

returning Kabul, Herat the home country, Afghanistan is quest for identity expressed by Laila.

The beginning of identity and prosperity in the life of Laila is reflected even by the end of drought and everyday rain in Kabul. "The drought has ended.... now it has been raining for days" (p. 396). Laila has returned Kabul. She lives with her children and she feels happy with Tariq. The drought of her life has ended and there is prosperity in her life. Laila and Tariq start making a school in their home country. "It was Tariq and Zaman who built the classroom by knocking down the wall between two adjacent rooms" (p. 400). It is making the social identity in Kabul. Laila has become a school teacher in Kabul. She teaches Farsi and she established her personal identity in her home country. Her daily teaching life style is described in this way. Laila passes beneath the sign and enters the classroom. The children are taking their seats, flipping notebooks open, chattering Aziza is talking to a girl in the adjacent row.... "Open your Farsi books, children" Laila says, dropping her own books on her desk (p. 401).

Laila ultimately achieves her quest for identity, making her struggles meaningful. She faces unexpected challenges and endures significant suffering to attain her dignified social identity. This illustrates the broader journey of establishing identity not just for Laila and Mariam, but for all Afghan women in real-life situations.

Mariam, despite being imprisoned, emerges as a determined and courageous woman. Born as an identity-less child, or "harami," she ultimately takes a bold step by killing Rasheed to protect both Laila and herself. Her transformation from an illegitimate beginning to a figure of legitimate strength is depicted in the following narrative.

She thought of her entry in the world, the harami child of a lowly villager, an unintended thing, a pitiable, regrettable accident. A weed and yet she was leaving the world as a woman who had loved and been loved back. She was leaving it as a friend, a compassion, a guardian. A mother a person of consequence at last no. It was not so bad, Mariam thought that she should die this

way. Not so bad. This was a legitimate end to a life of illegitimate beginnings (p. 361).

This extract highlights Mariam's lifelong struggle for identity, beginning from her birth as a "harami"—unwanted and pitiable. She married Rasheed in search of identity, but that relationship proved unsatisfactory. After killing him in self-defense, she found herself in prison, where she received love and respect from a jailor who acted as a friend, companion, guardian, and mother. Despite the circumstances, Mariam realized that her situation wasn't entirely negative; she gained a sense of legitimacy within the prison system. While other female inmates had committed lesser offenses, Mariam's act was seen as significant and extraordinary for a woman, acknowledged by her fellow prisoners. Thus, she achieved a form of institutional legitimacy in her life. Both Mariam and Laila's identities serve as a moral example for other Afghan women, demonstrating how to escape the confines of domestic violence and the daily struggles imposed by their male partners.

Conclusion

A Thousand Splendid Suns serves as a powerful moral guide for Afghan women, encouraging them to emulate Mariam and Laila in their fight against domestic violence and a male-dominated society. Women should not accept their suffering as fate; instead, they must break free from the confines of their homes and challenge the tradition of wearing the burqa, which renders them mere puppets to their husbands. They deserve to seek equality and justice while establishing their own identities within society. Women are vital members of the nation and have the potential to transform existing systems and values if they become proactive and empowered. They must refuse to surrender to the burdens imposed by a patriarchal structure. Restructuring society is essential, and Mariam and Laila stand as models for Afghan women, demonstrating the importance of taking action based on their realities. They should not remain silent during identity crises. Afghan women must pursue their dignified and respected identities because, without this effort, no one grants them their rightful place. They need to follow in the footsteps of Mariam and Laila for a brighter

future. The theory of patriarchy has become analogue in it.

Implication

It has got its voice for seeking not only the identity of women as such but also the identity of all the marginalized citizens to be identified and dignified ones in equal form as human beings.

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